

NUTRITION RECOMMENDATIONS FOR CARDIAC PATHOLOGIES

Abstract:

Key words:

Among non-drug methods of prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases, therapeutic nutrition is of great importance. Hypercholesterolemia is one of the main risk factors for the development of atherosclerosis and other heart and vascular diseases.

heart, disease, methodology, treatment, medicine, food.

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INTRODUCTION

Among non-drug methods of treatment and prevention of cardiovascular diseases (CVD), therapeutic nutrition is of particular importance. Food products, entering the body, are transformed in the process of metabolism into structural elements of cells, provide an adequate functional state of all organs and systems of the body, determine the state of health and life expectancy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The prominent Russian scientist M.I. Pevsner wrote:

"where there is no therapeutic nutrition, there is no rational treatment" [1]. The saying of Hippocrates is also well known: "Let food be your medicine, and medicine be your food."

In many cases, nutrition. enhances the effect of various types of therapy, prevents the

development of complications and the progression of the disease. At the same time, it is well known that hypercholesterolemia is one of the main risk factors for the development of atherosclerosis and other CVD. Excess cholesterol can enter the body with food (egg, butter, liver, etc.).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to take into account all these features and a wide variety of foods and substances in practical activities when organizing therapeutic nutrition, a computer program has been developed for automated compilation of an individual diet of therapeutic nutrition for hypercholesterolemia, taking into account the medical and social characteristics of the patient and the clinical picture of the disease. The program is based on the principles of a balanced diet [2], according to which the optimal amount and ratio of basic nutrients are preserved in the diet. At the same time, age, gender, weight ratios, the level of physical activity of the patient are taken into account and the individual energy value of the diet is calculated. The computer program makes it possible to significantly improve the quality of medical nutrition, thereby contributing to an increase in the effectiveness of the treatment process.

The urgent need to change the current situation has led to increased interest in the development of functional food products. Amaranth oil contains 67% polyunsaturated fatty acids (omega-6), lecithin, vitamin E and a large amount of squalene (up to 8%). It has been established that squalene is a powerful antitumor and immunostimulating agent.

For the first time, squalene was obtained from the liver of sharks, which contains only up to 1.5% squalene.

Amaranth contains a large amount of vitamins B, C, P, D, E. There are many macronutrients: potassium, calcium, sodium and trace elements: zinc, copper, chromium, iron, phosphorus, silicon and selenium, which is part of most hormones and enzymes, ensuring the normal functioning of various body systems.

It is very important that amaranth contains a sufficient amount of biologically active

substances: tocopherols, sterols, squalene, chlorophyll, choline, alcohols, steroids, phytosterols, carotenoids, pectin. The significant role of pectin in lowering cholesterol and triglycerides in the blood has been proven. Some types of amaranth contain up to 3% rutin in the leaves, which allows them to be considered as a source of vitamin P and used for hemorrhagic syndromes.

Due to the content of such a large number of various biologically active substances, amaranth has a restorative, anti-inflammatory and antitumor effect.

Amaranth flour is widely used in human food in the bakery and confectionery industry. Various salads and more are prepared from amaranth leaves. In animal husbandry, amaranth is widely used as feed for livestock, poultry and other animals.

Currently, amaranth is considered as a promising raw material for the food and pharmaceutical industry [14, 15, 16].

CONCLUSION

1. Among non-drug methods of prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases, therapeutic nutrition is of great importance.
2. The changes that have arisen in the diet of the population have caused the need to develop and put into practice functional food products, which include biologically active food additives (dietary supplements).
3. Soy and amaranth are among the most promising FPP in their composition and unique properties for use for the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases.

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